

METHODS OF INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF GEOGRAPHY LESSONS ON THE BASIS OF AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract. *This article discusses how to organize geography classes more efficiently, to make students interested in science, and to make it easier for teachers to deliver geographical processes to students in geography classes. The student is in the main place, the teacher should be the guide.*

Keywords: *geographical riddle, Who tells more information, When numbers speak, What for?*

In order to further increase students' interest in geography lessons, it is desirable to organize lessons in an interesting way. Some teachers complain that students are not interested in classes and spend more time in front of the phone and computer. One thinks that the reason for this is that the teachers are not able to organize the lessons in an interesting way.

" GEOGRAPHY RIDDLES ", " WHO TELLS A LOT OF INFORMATION?", " WHAT FOR? ", " WHEN THE NUMBERS ARE TALKING ", "DO NOT BE LEFT BEHIND", "AN INTELLIGENT STUDENT, "CONNECTIG SUBJECT INFORMATION WITH LIFE", "FIND YOUR PLACE" methods.

The first method. Taking into account the specific characteristics of the teaching classes, using the following geography riddles in the form of problematic situations in order to attract attention and interest in the lesson at the beginning of the lesson or in the process of working in groups - by dividing them into two groups and giving riddles to the groups in turn, giving them five seconds to think, 5-, 6-, 7-, 8-, 9- and 10 in the form of handouts The efficiency of the lessons would be higher if different methods were used in the first grade taking into account the age characteristics of the students.

Examples of **geography riddles**:

1. Talib lost his way,
Rosa stayed.
Map and plan too,
Compasses, gnomons too,
The rest is gone,
What should Talib do now ?
Let's go with my chart,
Looking at the trees,
Is it floating in the mountains ?

Answer: Identification by trees

2. Plants turn their faces to him,
The mouth of the ant nest is built,
The word "Australia" is attached to it.

What's the name of this side?

Answer: The south

3. Give it the right color,
Will give you information.

Answer: Map without inscription

4. Equator to Arctic,

Your friend Ghani is on his way .

To which latitude goes,

Tell me this Gani?

Answer: Towards northern latitude

By using the second method, it is possible to have the opportunity to evaluate the majority of students in the lesson. This method is called "**Who tells more information?**" is called, and it can be organized as follows: If there are several rows in the class, one student from each row goes to the blackboard and tells one piece of information on a certain topic one after the other, interruption in 5 seconds The student loses and sits down. The student who remains at the end and tells the most information is promoted as the winner.

The third method is called "**When the numbers speak**", the teacher writes frames related to the topics covered on the board. Students should quickly explain what these numbers mean. For example, 11022 m, 4643 m, 4484 m, 13, 1507, 1498, 1595, 1966, 1976... 11022 m - Mariana Trench...

The fourth method is "**WHAT FOR?**" method for use in Geography classes, for example, the regional (local) environmental problem that arose in Central Asia and Uzbekistan is the problem of the drying up of the Aral Sea, which has recently turned into a world (global) environmental problem. "What for?" scheme method is a chain of thoughts to determine the initial causes of the problem. Develops and activates systematic, creative, analytical thinking. It is a method of problem identification, problem solving, analysis, and planning that requires students to ask "Why?" they are familiar with the rules of drawing up a scheme. They represent the problem in separate small groups. "What for?" they ask a question and draw, and write an answer to this question. This process continues until the root cause of the problem is identified. 4 times to determine the root cause of the Aral Sea water drying problem Why? the question will be answered:

1. Why did the water level of the Aral Sea decrease? Answer: Because Amudarya and Syrdarya, which flow into the Aral Sea, have flowed a small amount of water. 2. Why did the Amudarya and Syrdarya flow a small amount of water into the Aral Sea? Answer: Because many canals have been dug from Amudarya and Syrdarya. 3. Why were many canals dug from Amudarya and Syrdarya? Answer: Because canals were dug to develop deserts and release water.

4. Why were the deserts exploited? Answer: Because in 1948, the former Union government adopted the decision "On the development of reserves and wastelands". The main ways to improve the ecological situation in the Aral Bay region are: providing the population with clean drinking water, regularly sending water to the dry riverbeds, lakes, building sand to block the movement of the wind in the dry part of the sea. It consists of strengthening with plants, improving land melioration, and expanding the areas of pastures and hayfields.

The fifth method is **"Don't stay behind!"** If the "method" is used in the part of the lesson to repeat the learned topic, to strengthen the learned topic, it is possible to evaluate more students, and to further increase the activity of the students. To use this method in 6th and 7th grades, two students will go to the blackboard, one of them will write MOUNTAINS, and the other will write RIVERS. On the table, the inscriptions with the names of rivers and mountains are placed upside down, the students sitting at the desk go out and read one inscription, and when the name of the river appears, the student holding the RIVERS inscription takes one step. walks forward, on the contrary, if the name of the mountain comes out, the student holding the inscription MOUNTAINS walks forward one step. In the 9th-10th grades, if we explain every topic covered in the REPUBLIC and beyond in connection with different areas of our life, if we give real life examples, not only our lesson is interesting, but by writing the names of MONARCHY, FEDERAL and UNITAR, EUROPE and ASIA, the countries are correct. it is possible to test students' knowledge about Moreover, by explaining that the importance of our subject in life is incomparable, we will increase the students' interest in learning.

The sixth method **"Connecting subject information with life"**. In this method, if the teacher mainly explains the information of the subject in connection with various areas of our life, the subject will be well understood by the student and will not be forgotten.

On April 12-13, 2022, in an interview with the initiator and head of the PISA (PISA) program, Andreas Schleicher, it was criticized that one of the shortcomings of the Uzbekistan education system is that education is not connected with life. Based on this, it would be appropriate to deepen this relationship during lessons in schools. Because in this way, we will increase students' interest in science and make it easier for them to understand the topic. For example, based on the change in the National Curriculum, in the 8th grade, in the subject of the natural geography of Uzbekistan, the subject of the soil of Uzbekistan is the use of local fertilizers to increase the fertility of the soil, and the cultivation of food products useful for our natural health. possible, and we will encourage students to do socially useful work, it would be useful to explain how to act during an earthquake when talking about earthquakes in the cities of Bukhara and Gazli on the topic of the Lower Zarafshan natural geographical district. Such examples can be used in every subject from every subject. In the 9th grade, it is possible to develop domestic tourism and direct young people to entrepreneurship by talking about economic regions in the chapter on the territorial organization of Uzbekistan's economy, by seeing their unique nature, historical and cultural monuments.

The seventh method is called **an intelligent student**, and in this method, by using Smart questions, it serves to increase the effectiveness of the lesson and increase the interest of students in lessons. For example, in the 9th grade, in the United States of America:

1. What do the 13 bow arrows in the eagle's claws on the National Emblem of the USA mean?

2. What should be in the Christmas party? (J: turkey meat)

3. After the laying of gas pipelines in the USA, the smell of raw meat is mixed with the gas. What is the reason for this?

On the subject of transport: In 1992, he was included in the Guinness Book of Records for setting a record within the transport network. He stopped at 60 places and was able to increase the speed to 36.5 km/h. Which transport network is this? (J: Elevator).

Find your place! In the method, it is useful to imagine the place of geographical objects given to the subjects as continents or their place on the Earth. In the 7th grade, on the subject of the World Ocean, 4 students will have to go to the blackboard and take notes with the names of the oceans and stand in order according to the area of 4 oceans (6 students according to the area of 6 continents).

When using the methods given above, teachers can achieve great results if they take into account creativity, uniqueness of classes, and age characteristics of students.

Our lessons would be more interesting if we explained the natural geography of Uzbekistan according to the depth of depressions, mountain peaks according to their height, rivers according to their length, etc. in a game style.

In conclusion, the above-mentioned interactive methods, aimed at ensuring the effective and efficient teaching process, make a significant difference in students' timely and effective mastering of geography lessons, and further increase the effectiveness of the lesson. .

By using the methods given above, creativity of teachers, originality of classes, taking into account the age characteristics of students, they can improve students' mastery of geography, as well as raise the status of the subject. they would have made their due contribution in the high cause.

REFERENCES

1. Rafikov V. Interesting geography. T. 2010, [120 p]
2. Republican Education Center "Methodology of Teaching Geography in General Secondary Education" (methodical manual). Tashkent. 2020 year.
3. Rafikov V. "Interesting geography". T. 2010, [120 b]
4. Vahobov H, Mirzamahmudov O.T "Methodology of teaching geography" methodical manual. Namangan. 2016 year.
5. Mirakmalov M.T., Avezov M.M., Nazaraliyeva E.E. "Practical exercises in natural geography". Tashkent. 2015 year.
6. "Marifat" newspaper. 2018 year. No. 75, [page 6.
7. "Methodology of General Education" magazine, September 2020, No. 9, [117 p]
8. The collection of materials of the regional scientific-practical conference "Innovative approaches in natural sciences: solutions and perspectives" of the Department of Public Education of the Navoi Region of the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Navoi. 2021, [pages 79-82]
9. Pedagoglar.uz "For teachers". October 31, 2021.
10. Research "Scientific-practical research in Uzbekistan". 2020 year. #20, [page 164]